

HOW TO PERSIST A PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER?

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Abstract - Many French archival services use persistent identifiers to facilitate access to archives. However, few studies have addressed the sustainability of these identifiers. This can raise questions when these identifiers are employed to identify digital archives preserved in digital repositories.

The Vitam program, which develops the Vitam digital recordkeeping software on behalf of the French government, carried out a study in collaboration with the Vitam user community in 2021. The goal was to improve knowledge of the use of persistent identifiers, particularly ARK identifiers, as well as their lifecycle and the requirements regarding their sustainability. The study also aimed to define the features required in the Vitam software to guarantee a long-term preservation of this type of identifier, whatever happens. Finally, it also made sure that their use could be adapted to different user contexts.

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commonly used for research data, alongside other unique identification systems - International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI) [5], Identifiers and Repositories for the French Higher Education and Research System (IdRef) [6][7], etc.- used in other contexts. Currently, there are more than 360 French institutions registered in the ARK Registry [8]. Its use is also mentioned alongside that of Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) [9] and ISNIs by the "French General Interoperability Repository" for the public sector [10].

While persistent identifiers are now widely used in French archival services for online archival dissemination, their durability has not yet been tested in the context of digital recordkeeping. In 2021, the Vitam Program, which develops the Vitam digital recordkeeping software on behalf of the French government and relies on a community of users from both the public and private sectors, was asked by one of its users how to integrate ARK identifiers into the Vitam software, in the context of a data migration.

An initial analysis showed that the unique identification of archives provided by the Vitam software did not fully cover the user's needs, nor did the models proposed by the Data Exchange Standard for Archiving (SEDA) [11], the data model used by public archival services in France.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Context And Objectives

Among the various existing persistent identification systems [1], the Archival Resource Key (ARK) identification system [2][3] is more widespread within French heritage institutions than the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) system [4], which is more

Rather than meeting this single user need, the Vitam Program invited its community to increase its skills on the subject, and to work together on defining the features required to manage persistent identifiers, whether they are ARK identifiers or any other type of identifiers. The objective was to provide the most generic solution and to have it implemented in the Vitam software.

B. Methodology

The study was carried out by a working group which was led by the Vitam program team and included the interested users of the Vitam software. The group's objectives were:

- To increase skills,
- To analyze the current uses of persistent identifiers in a digital recordkeeping context,
- To define together the expected features for managing persistent identifiers in the Vitam software.

The working group focused mainly on ARK identifiers, which are more widely used in French heritage institutions, while ensuring that other persistent identification systems were considered when required.

The study was performed in two phases:

1) *A phase of definition* provided a clear understanding of how persistent identifiers can be used, and how they are used in the French context. The French National Library (BnF), a reference in this field in France [12][13][14], shared its feedback on the use of ARK identifiers. So did other institutions using the Vitam software: a third-party archiver – the National Computer Center for Higher Education (CINES) – and two archival services – the Departmental Archives of Hérault and the Departmental Archives of Gironde, which already employ persistent identifiers in their own contexts. The working group was also given the results of an internal survey carried out at the time by the Interministerial Service of the French Archives (SIAF) to assess the use of ARK identifiers by the French public archival services [15][16].

2) *A phase of discussions* then aimed to design together the requirements for managing persistent identifiers in the Vitam software.

II. INITIAL OBSERVATIONS

As in the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Reference Model [17][18], the Vitam software distinguishes between the binary part of the information object (data object), the technical description of this digital material (technical metadata), the descriptive information (descriptive metadata), the archivist's management metadata (management metadata) and finally the file plan (representation information) [19]. It models them according to the Data Exchange Standard for Archiving (SEDA) [11].

The latter follows the same logic as the International Standard Archival Description (Isad(G)) [20] and the Encoded Archival Description (EAD) [21]:

- ArchiveUnit (Unit), which stands for either a single file or an item, with descriptive and management metadata and the hierarchical structure,
- DataObject (Object), representing the object to be preserved, physical or digital, including its technical metadata,
- DataObjectGroup (ObjectGroup), standing for a set of data objects that represent the same unit but in the form of different data objects (paper, PDF, Word, etc.) [19].

Fig. 1. Data representation

The SEDA standard contains several fields corresponding to an identifier:

- For ArchiveUnits: position of the ArchiveUnit in the file plan of the originating agency (FilePlanPosition), identifier assigned to objects by the digital repository (SystemId), identifier provided by the originating agency's software (OriginatingSystemId), identifier given by the archival agency (ArchivalAgencyArchiveUnitIdentifier), identifier assigned by the originating agency

(OriginatingAgencyArchiveUnitIdentifier) or by the transferring agency (TransferringAgencyArchiveUnitIdentifier).

- For DataObjects: identifier assigned to data objects (DataObjectSystemId) and identifier given to groups of data objects (DataObjectGroupSystemId), physical identifier of a physical data object (PhysicalId) for physical objects only [11].

When transferring the Submission Information Package (SIP), the Vitam software assigns a unique identifier for each ArchiveUnit, DataObject and DataObjectGroup by instance of the software [19]. In addition, it stores in the Archival Information Package (AIP) most of the metadata fields defined by the SEDA standard if they are present to identify an ArchiveUnit or a DataObject.

However, it does not store the identifier assigned to DataObjects (DataObjectSystemId) and restricts the use of DataObjectGroupSystemId and SystemId metadata, which it uses in its acknowledgment of receipt to display the technical identifiers it generates.

While one of the metadata fields could be used for ArchiveUnits, the model needs to be extended for ObjectGroups. Furthermore, the fields available to identify ArchiveUnits may be used differently from one user to another. Finally, the unique identifier generated by the digital repository is only unique on the platform. When an archive is transferred, it will appear in the Dissemination Information Package (DIP) and SIP exchanged, and in the acknowledgment of receipt. However, it will not be kept in the new AIPs. The working group's discussions were based on these observations.

III. WHAT CAN PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS BE USED FOR?

The Vitam program's approach has been to identify the use cases around a feature, before defining precisely how it should be implemented in the software. This method has also helped define the scope and reasons behind the choices to be made.

As part of this study, four use cases involving the use of ARK identifiers in a digital recordkeeping context were analyzed:

- 1) The *CINES* carries out archiving on behalf of higher education institutions. Its digital repository assigns an ARK identifier to archival packages and files when archives are

transferred, and it provides them in the acknowledgment of receipt transmitted to the originating agencies, so that they can use them when requesting access to their documents. As part of its system migration to the Vitam software, the *CINES* wondered how to retrieve these identifiers in the new system, and how to generate new identifiers in it.

- 2) At the *Departmental Archives of Gironde*, a dedicated software, which is not integrated into the digital repository, generates, imports, centralizes and exports ARK identifiers for archival packages and ArchiveUnits, regardless of their position in the file plan. It does likewise for the vocabularies referenced in the thesauri in use. The identifiers serve as a reference and can be found at all ArchiveUnit levels of archival packages [22][23].
- 3) At the *Departmental Archives of Hérault*, digital archives and finding aids are given an ARK identifier when they are published on the Archives' website, after they have been described [24]. The goal is to facilitate access to online archives and finding aids.
- 4) Finally, the working group studied the possibility of transferring digital archives, previously held by an institution that assigned persistent identifiers with its own Name Assigning Authority Number (NAAN), to another archival service. The latter may not have a persistent identification policy or may have one that is totally different from that of the transferring institution.

A parallel was also drawn between persistent identifiers and the use of references associated with paper archives. For example, an archival service in charge of records management usually has a policy for identifying paper files. Once these have been transferred to an archival service in charge of long-term preservation, the service will assign a new reference. There are two possible uses to preserve and reuse these two identifiers:

- The archival service responsible for long-term preservation does not keep track of the old reference. The reference it assigns takes precedence in its search tools and for its users. The archival service in charge of records management may have retained the

old reference and ensures the link between the old and new references. This enables it to fulfill access requests from originating agencies.

- The archival service in charge of long-term preservation keeps track of the old reference and creates a new one. Depending on whether the requester is from an originating agency or is a general reader, the archive can be found using either the old or the new reference.

For all these archival services, persistent identifiers are intended to provide a non-significant and unambiguous reference to the archive, either at the time of transfer or afterward. Unlike the unique identifier generated by the digital repository, this identifier is meant to persist even in the context of archive transfers or platform migration.

IV. WHAT QUESTIONS HAD TO BE ANSWERED?

Based on these examples, the working group focused on answering several questions aimed at defining the Vitam software's feature for managing persistent identifiers.

A. Generating Persistent Identifiers

1. What Should A Persistent Identifier Be Assigned To?

A digital repository must be able to assign persistent identifiers at different levels of the archival package. An ArchiveUnit associated with a DataObject can generically be given an ARK identifier (case 1). However, identifiers are not systematically assigned to all the ArchiveUnits included in a file plan. Depending on what it is intended to identify, the technical metadata referencing the DataObject may also be referenced by a specific persistent identifier (case 2), by a qualifier corresponding to the DataObject's use or use and version (case 3), or by a combination of both (case 4).

Fig. 2. Different cases of attribution of persistent identifiers

2. Which Tool Assigns Persistent Identifiers?

Persistent identifiers can be assigned by the Vitam software, which is a specific need expressed by the CINES, by an external software connected to the Vitam software, as it will happen at the Departmental Archives of Gironde [22][23], or by a software which is not connected to the digital repository using the Vitam software.

When providing ARK identifiers, the Vitam software must either be able to assign persistent identifiers, or simply retrieve them, or allow both uses, as in the case of the CINES, which has already assigned ARK identifiers and will use the Vitam software to generate new ARK identifiers.

Fig. 3. Different software assigning persistent identifiers

3. How To Manage NAAN Attribution?

The digital repository can retrieve an identifier from one or more originating agencies. This means it must be able to manage resources with different Name Assigning Authority Numbers (NAAN).

At the same time, it can create persistent identifiers, which requires it to assign identifiers for a single institution (single NAAN) or several organizations (case of third-party archivers and joint projects). The Vitam software must consequently be able to adapt and, if necessary, assign ARK identifiers with different NAANs.

If the given ARK identifier comes from the same organization (identical NAAN), a new NAAN may not be assigned, and a new ARK identifier may not be generated.

4. How To Model Persistent Identifiers?

The Data Exchange Standard for Archiving (SEDA) [11] includes a certain number of descriptive metadata corresponding to identifiers (reference assigned by the archival service, by the originating agency, etc.). However, these identifiers can be used for different needs than qualifying a persistent identifier. In addition, the SEDA does not currently contain any technical metadata for the persistent identification of the data objects themselves.

Using specific metadata for persistent identifiers, which can be applied to both ArchiveUnits and DataObjects, without the risk of them being used for other referencing (as could be the case with existing metadata) seemed to be the right choice.

The PREMIS (PREservation Metadata Implementation Strategies) standard [25] provides a model for persistent identifiers (value and type).

The working group relied on these two standards and worked on a model that is intended to be generic, to integrate it into the SEDA, which can be extended. This data model defines a dedicated metadata section for persistent identification (PersistentIdentifier), in which a persistent identifier must be specified through a value (PersistentIdentifierContent) and a type (PersistentIdentifierType), such as ARK, DOI, etc. Where applicable, additional contextual metadata may also be provided, including the origin of the identifier (PersistentIdentifierOrigin) and a reference (PersistentIdentifierReference). This model applies to both ArchiveUnits and DataObjects. Finally, two metadata have been proposed to qualify a DataObject, alongside the existing metadata (DataObjectVersion): its usage (DataObjectUse) and its version (DataObjectNumber).

```
<ArchiveUnit id="ID22">
  <Content>
    <DescriptionLevel>Item</DescriptionLevel>
    <Title>Image.jpg</Title>
    <OriginatingAgencyArchiveUnitIdentifier>AU0003</OriginatingAgencyArchiveUnitIdentifier>
    <TransactedDate>2016-06-03T15:28:00</TransactedDate>
    <PersistentIdentifier>
      <PersistentIdentifierType>doi</PersistentIdentifierType>
      <PersistentIdentifierOrigin>OriginatingAgency</PersistentIdentifierOrigin>
      <PersistentIdentifierReference>Public Library</PersistentIdentifierReference>
      <PersistentIdentifierContent>doi:10.1522/cia.ada.con</PersistentIdentifierContent>
    </PersistentIdentifier>
    <PersistentIdentifier>
      <PersistentIdentifierType>ark</PersistentIdentifierType>
      <PersistentIdentifierOrigin>ArchivalAgency</PersistentIdentifierOrigin>
      <PersistentIdentifierReference>National Archives</PersistentIdentifierReference>
      <PersistentIdentifierContent>ark:/22567/001a957db5eadaac</PersistentIdentifierContent>
    </PersistentIdentifier>
  </Content>
  <DataObjectReference>
    <DataObjectGroupReferenceId>ID20</DataObjectGroupReferenceId>
  </DataObjectReference>
</ArchiveUnit>
```

Fig. 4. ArchiveUnit with two persistent identifiers

```
<DataObjectGroup id="ID20">
  <BinaryDataObject id="ID21">
    <DataObjectVersion>BinaryMaster_1</DataObjectVersion>
    <PersistentIdentifier>
      <PersistentIdentifierType>ark</PersistentIdentifierType>
      <PersistentIdentifierOrigin>OriginatingAgency</PersistentIdentifierOrigin>
      <PersistentIdentifierReference>Museum</PersistentIdentifierReference>
      <PersistentIdentifierContent>ark:/22567/001a957db5eadaac</PersistentIdentifierContent>
    </PersistentIdentifier>
    <Content/Label2.jppeg/Uri>
    <MessageDigest algorithm="SHA-512">7c1531396583c478b2d66ad1a4b34e250d6751ee4b39e546a77f9
    c0d71ccefee5e2661b457f9e946a4e2d45d831058d3f61c1914b7d45a168bace27f1d6fc/MessageDigest>
    <Size>3862</Size>
    <FormatIdentification>
      <FormatLiteral>JPG</FormatLiteral>
      <MimeType>image/jpeg</MimeType>
      <FormatId>45</FormatId>
    </FormatIdentification>
    <FileInfo>
      <Filename>Image.jpg</Filename>
      <LastModified>2021-05-14T16:02:35.0000</LastModified>
    </FileInfo>
    <DataObjectUse>BinaryMaster</DataObjectUse>
    <DataObjectNumber>1</DataObjectNumber>
  </BinaryDataObject>
</DataObjectGroup>
```

Fig. 5. DataObject with a persistent identifier

B. What Should A Digital Repository Do?

1. Ingest

The digital repository must allow persistent identifiers to be assigned at the level of the whole platform, or per tenant in a joint context. It must also retrieve archives that have already been identified with persistent identifiers. Finally, it must allow both types of use.

The persistent identifier scope (platform, organization) must be configurable. The type of item to be identified must also be configurable (description of a digital object, digital object itself, archival package, all items), as well as the way to identify this item (simple ARK identifier, ARK identifier with qualifier – for files only, simple qualifier – for files only).

After transferring archives, the acknowledgment of receipt must be able to provide a list of the archives that have been transferred, including their persistent identifiers.

2. Access

The digital repository must allow archives to be searched and found through their persistent identifiers, whether these identifiers are made up exclusively of ARK identifiers or contain a qualifier. It must also be able to transfer archives with persistent identifiers to an external web site for public dissemination.

If identification has not been carried out at the time of ingest, it must be possible to perform it later.

3. Disposal

If archives with a persistent identifier have been disposed of, the digital repository must be able to indicate that these archives are no longer available due to disposal. If necessary, it can redirect to a version of the object, if versions of the DataObject have been removed.

4. Archive Transfer

Archives with persistent identifier can be transferred to another repository — for example, at the end of a retention period, when they are moved from an archival service in charge of records management to an archival service in charge of long-term preservation. This is a critical moment when the guarantee of identifier persistence may be compromised.

The working group examined several potential scenarios to maintain the persistence of the identifier, or at least to address the varying levels of commitment associated with persistent identification [3].

There are three possible scenarios:

- If archives are transferred from a repository using the Vitam software to another repository also using the Vitam software, it is important to check that they are transferred with their persistent identifiers and that these are not modified: the persistent identifier must be the same, as must the qualifier. The Vitam software would then be able to guarantee the sustainability of the ARK identifier, qualifier included.
- If archives are transferred from a repository that does not use the Vitam software to a repository that use the Vitam software, the persistent identifier must be the same. It will be possible to keep the complete persistent identifier as metadata, with or without qualifier.
- On the other hand, if archives are transferred from a repository using the Vitam software to a repository that does not use the Vitam software, the ARK identifier must be the same. But the qualifier set in the ARK identifier may not be preserved.

As a result of the archive transfer, depending on the organization and level of commitment chosen, when searching for transferred archives by using their persistent identifier, the originating repository can either indicate that the resources are no longer available due to the transfer, or provide access to the resources now available on another platform via redirection.

On the other hand, the recipient repository has several options. It can assume responsibility for providing access to the archive using the ARK identifiers it has received from the originating repository. It can offer a redirection service between the old ARK identifiers and the new ones it has assigned, so that a user can access the resource either through the old or the new identifier. It can also provide no redirection, leaving this responsibility to the originating agency, or offer a mixed service.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Beyond proposing a reference model, this study, conducted under the Vitam program, helped identify key questions that must be considered when implementing persistent identifiers. These apply both to digital repository developers offering persistent identification services, and to archival services responsible for preserving records tagged with such identifiers.

It also revealed a lack of practical experience with the use and sustainability of persistent identifiers in digital recordkeeping contexts—particularly in France, where they are still primarily used for the online dissemination of digitized archives rather than for long-term archiving.

After theory came practice. In 2022–2023, the study led to a third phase, which included a technical analysis carried out by the Vitam program's IT team, followed by the implementation of the feature in the Vitam software, in accordance with the study's findings.

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